

Winter *Camelina sativa* varieties as a source of biodiversity in culture agroforestry

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One of the main challenges facing agricultural areas today is the limited amount of agricultural land with an ever-increasing population. Increasing crop productivity results in a reduction of biodiversity which is the foundation of a sustainable ecosystem. In line with the strategy for the restoration of biodiversity, the aim of this paper is to present the potential of the traditional oilseed plant of Greater Poland which is *Camelina sativa* L. It is a plant with low soil and fertilizer requirements. Winter varieties of flaxseed are not as widespread as spring varieties, although recently there has been increased interest in the area of its cultivation. In Poland, four varieties of winter flax are protected in the Book of Exclusive Rights: Lenka, Luna, Przybrodzka and Maczuga raised at the Poznań University of Life Sciences (PULS). Based on a long-term study conducted on PULS, it can be concluded that the length of the vegetation period of spring forms is about 100-130 days and that of winter forms is 280 to 300 days. The false flax plant's height varies from 50 to 90 cm for spring forms and from 80 to 120 cm for winter forms. The weight of 1,000 seeds ranges from 0.8 to 1.6 g, depending on the variety. In parallel with the field tests, chemical analyses were conducted. In connection with the purpose of the false flax seeds for the production of camelina oil, the fatty acid profile was analyzed, using gas chromatography (GC-MS). In 2015-2022, a field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design at the Agricultural Research Station Hand of the PULS. Field management followed standard agricultural practice. The research was conducted on two spring varieties Oliva and Omega. Comparing the results obtained for the winter varieties with the spring varieties, it was found that the winter genotypes had a higher concentration of essential fatty acids than the spring forms. Linoleic acid (C18:2 ω -6) accounted for 13% of the total fatty acid content in spring varieties and 15% in winter varieties. The content of α -linolenic acid (C18: 3 ω -3) was significantly higher in spring varieties (40%) than in winter varieties (36%). Overall, the PUFA to MUFA ratio for spring varieties was higher (1.44:1) than for winter varieties (1.35:1). Studies conducted indicate the great potential of winter varieties of *Camelina sativa* seeds.

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